

Cohort-resolved excess mortality in Germany (2000-2024): Patterns and implications for the SARS-CoV-2 era

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Abstract

Understanding the impact of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic on mortality requires more than aggregate statistics. While whole-population indicators have informed policy, they risk concealing subgroup-specific patterns. We analysed all-cause mortality in Germany from 2000 to 2024 using a weekly, cohort-resolved framework across 15 age groups to detect excess and under-mortality before, during, and after the pandemic.

Expected mortality was modelled using exponential trends from two decades of pre-pandemic data. Deviations from expectation were quantified as normalised excess all-cause mortality rates (NEAMR), enabling the identification of significant, age-specific anomalies.

We found sustained excess mortality in adults aged 75-79 and 35-49 from late 2021 through 2024 – patterns absent in whole-population trends. Conversely, cohorts aged 30-34 and 55-59 showed persistent under-mortality. Earlier peaks in older cohorts (e.g., 85-89 in 2003, 95+ in 2013) suggest generational vulnerabilities potentially linked to early-life adversity.

Cross-correlation analyses indicate that associations between NEAMR and SARS-CoV-2 mRNA injection rates often diverge from expected protective patterns, especially during the 2021 ‘alpha’-to-‘delta’ transition. These findings highlight the need for high-resolution mortality surveillance. Cohort-resolved analysis reveals signals that aggregate data obscure, offering a more accurate assessment of public health outcomes across demographic groups.

Key words: age cohorts; prognosis model

1. Introduction

Until 2009, the global public health community broadly adhered to a consensus definition of pandemics – namely, that they involve the emergence of a novel pathogen to which there is no human immunity, and which causes widespread illness and substantial mortality. The World Health Organization (WHO), for instance, described an influenza pandemic as occurring “when a new influenza virus appears against which the human population has no immunity, resulting in epidemics worldwide with enormous numbers of deaths and illness” [1]. Central to such assessments was the empirical evaluation of (excess) all-cause mortality (AM) – a robust and objective indicator of population-level health crises.

After 2009, however, the definitional framework employed by the WHO underwent notable revisions [2]. These changes effectively decoupled the pandemic label from quantitative

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criteria such as morbidity and mortality thresholds. This shift allowed the declaration of a pandemic in March 2020 [3] – in the case of SARS-CoV-2 – on grounds that no longer explicitly required demonstrable excess mortality (EM) or widespread health system failure.

In Germany, this declaration had immediate and far-reaching implications. Following the WHO’s announcement on March 11th, 2020, the German Bundestag, on March 25th, 2020, enacted emergency legislation that granted the federal and local governments powers to restrict fundamental civil liberties. This included limitations on freedom of movement and assembly, the right to bodily autonomy, and the inviolability of the home, justified by an “epidemic situation of national importance” (“epidemische Lage von nationaler Tragweite”) in response to the global spread of SARS-CoV-2.

Given the global nature of the pandemic declaration, it is both valid and necessary to revisit its empirical foundations using historical benchmarks. One such benchmark is the magnitude of excess all-cause mortality (EAM) – a well-established metric. In prior analyses for Germany [4, 5], we and others translated the pre-2009 WHO criteria into a formal EAM framework and found no evidence of significant EAM during 2020. Nor was there a discernible crisis-level mortality burden during the 2019/2020 flu season (not even with its early 2020 tail [4, fig. 1]), nor in the subsequent 2020/2021 season – with the initiation of a mass SARS-CoV-2-mRNA injection (mRNA-I) campaign on December 27th, 2020. That season saw approximately 27,600 excess deaths, a figure comparable to that of the 2017/2018 flu season, which recorded around 25,100 excess deaths [6, p.47]. By contrast, the two intermittent flu seasons (2018/2019 and 2019/2020) had recorded under-mortalities of about -22,000 persons each.

The 2021/2022 flu season, in contrast, was marked by an EAM of approximately 31,100 individuals [4, tab. 2]. This occurred in the aftermath of a sustained mRNA-I campaign and multiple lockdowns, with widespread societal, psychological, and physiological consequences, including mandatory masking and healthcare delays. The arrival and predominance of the SARS-CoV-2 ‘omicron’ variant (B.1.1.529) in late 2021 – widely considered milder – complicates causal attribution. The apparent severity of this flu season thus cannot be readily explained by viral characteristics alone.

This study extends our previous work [4] by examining age-stratified, weekly EAM data in Germany from 2020 through 2024. Our goal is twofold. First, we investigate whether pandemic-level mortality signals may have been masked at the population level but remain detectable within specific age cohorts. Second, we assess whether age-resolved EAM correlates temporally with other epidemiological variables, in particular, PCR-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 incidence [7], and mRNA-I rates during the global immunisation campaign.

Our primary tool is the robust and minimally assumption-laden indicator of EAM, analysed at weekly resolution. We report not only significant seasonal EAM in older cohorts (as typically seen with influenza), but also unusually persistent and significant EAM among individuals aged 35 to 49 years – particularly from autumn 2021 onward, with distinct waves extending into 2024. Cross-correlation analyses suggest that these EAM patterns may be temporally associated with infection and mRNA-I waves, raising questions that warrant thorough further investigation.

2. Methods

2.1. Abbreviations and mathematical symbols

All essential abbreviations as well as their respective mathematical symbols used throughout this work are summarised in Table 1.

2.2. Data acquisition and curation

A brief synopsis of the German data sources that we based the present analysis and model development on.

2.2.1. Death data

Earlier (2000-2020) weekly AMC data were taken from the Destatis (German office for national statistics) webpage at [8]. More current (2021-2024) weekly AMC data were likewise taken from the Destatis webpage at [9]. The finest age cohort resolution available on a weekly scale were the fifteen cohorts of ‘0-29’, ‘30-34’, ‘35-39’, ‘40-44’, ‘45-49’, ‘50-54’, ‘55-59’, ‘60-64’, ‘65-69’, ‘70-74’, ‘75-79’, ‘80-84’, ‘85-89’, ‘90-94’, and ‘95+’ year old. Particularly when comparing time courses of EAMC with those of mRNA-I and PCR testing (see below), this fine resolution was not meaningful and therefore aggregated to match cohort definitions, yielding the seven age cohorts of ‘0-29’, ‘30-39’, ‘40-49’, ‘50-59’, ‘60-69’, ‘70-79’, and ‘80+’ year old.

Table 1: Abbreviations and mathematical symbols used throughout the study.

abbreviation { symbol }	meaning	description
SARS-CoV-2	Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Corona Virus 2	term used consistently for the virus; originally (and more appropriately) named 2019-nCoV
SP	spike protein	the spike protein of the SARS-CoV-2 shell
mRNA-I	SARS-CoV-2-mRNA injection	injection of any dose of lipid-particle-coated modified messenger RNA that codes for the SP
$\{ N_{\text{coh}} \}$ or $\{ N_{\text{pop}} \}$	cohort or population size	number of individuals in a given age cohort or the whole population, respectively
$\{ t \}$	time	represented in calendar weeks since the year 2000
AM	all-cause mortality	deaths from any cause
AMC $\{ D_{AM} \}$	all-cause mortality count	number of deaths recorded within a given interval (week, year, season)
$\{ D_{AM,\text{coh}} \}$	cohort-specific mortality count	AMC for a specific age cohort
AMR $\{ r_{AM,\text{coh}} \}$	all-cause mortality rate	ratio of AMC to the size of the corresponding cohort
expAMR	expected AMR	model estimate for r_{AM} at a certain time t
$\{ r_{AM,\text{coh}}^{\text{exp}}(t) \}$	normalised AMR	AMR normalised to its value in the reference year (2000)
NAMR	expected NAMR	model-predicted NAMR for a given cohort and time
expNAMR	normalised excess AMR	relative deviation of AMR from expected values: $(r_{AM} - r_{AM}^{\text{exp}})/r_{AM}^{\text{exp}}$
$\{ \tilde{r}_{AM,\text{coh}}^{\text{exp}}(t) \}$	excess all-cause mortality count	observed AMC minus expected AMC (expAMC)
NEAMR	Robert-Koch-Institut	Germany's national agency for disease control and prevention
EAMC	European Centre for Disease prevention and Control	EU-wide public health body for disease surveillance
RKI	calendar week	ISO-standard week numbering used throughout the analysis
ECDC	flu season	commonly defined as lasting from CW40 of the starting year to CW20 of the subsequent year (CW40-subscw20) [6, p. 13,17]
CW	flu season 1 of a year	CW04-CW20 of a given year, i.e. second half of an interannual fls
fls	flu season 2 of a year	CW40 of a year to CW03 of the subsequent year (CW40-subscw03), i.e. first half of an interannual fls
$\text{fls}_{1,\text{year}}$	summer season	time of the year that is not a fls, i.e. CW21-CW39
$\text{fls}_{2,\text{year}}$	model parameters	parameters for exponential fitting of expNAMR curves per cohort
sus_{year}		
$\{ a_{\text{coh}}, b_{\text{coh}} \}$		

2.2.2. Demographic data

The demographic (age cohort) distribution between 2000 and 2020 (based on the 2011 census) and its presumable distribution onwards (based on the most plausible scenario, the default model variant V1) were taken from the Destatis webpage at [10]. The finest age cohort resolution available on a yearly scale the 101 age cohorts ‘0-1’, ‘1-2’, . . . , ‘99-100’. The demography within a single year was assumed not to change at all, i.e. stayed constant in our analysis for every week of the corresponding year. This included the omission of potential birthdays within a year [5], which was assumed to play only a minor role within a five-year-cohort-resolution setting.

2.2.3. PCR-positive test data

The curation of the PCR-positive data set, likewise provided by the RKI as “accompanying data to the weekly report” [11], turned out to be similarly challenging. In this report, the time interval ranged from CW12 in 2020 to CW40 in 2023, the age cohorts were ‘0-4’, ‘5-14’, ‘15-34’, ‘35-59’, ‘60-79’, and ‘80+’ years, such that a direct correspondence to the above age cohorts was not straight forward. As a solution, we conducted a spline interpolation between the median points of the presented age cohorts, i.e. 2, 10, 25, 47, and 70 years, to obtain estimates for the median points of the six age cohorts above, i.e. 15, 35, 45, 55, 65, and 75 years. Data for the age cohort ‘80+’ were simply kept as presented. In the result section, we refer to ‘normalised test incidence’ meaning the weekly number of persons tested positive within an age cohort divided by the size of this cohort.

2.2.4. Data on SARS-CoV-2 variants

The ECDC made relative occurrences of various SARS-CoV-2 variants available [12] between CW01 in 2020 and CW43 in 2023. From this data set, we extracted the values for Germany. No age cohort resolution was available. In this work, we distinguished between the four variants ‘alpha’ (B.1.1.7), ‘delta’ (B.1.617.2), ‘omicron’ (B.1.1.529, XBB.1.5, XBB.1.5+F456L, BA.1, BA.2, BA.2.75, BA.4, BA.5, BQ.1), and ‘others’ (Beta (B.1.351), epsilon (B.1.427/B.1.429), eta (B.1.525), B.1.616, gamma (P.1), theta (P.3), kappa (B.1.617.1), B.1.620, lambda (C.37), UNK, B.1.621).

2.2.5. mRNA-I data

Compiling a concise and consistent data set comprising weekly mRNA-I rates among age cohorts provided a considerable challenge. Originally, the RKI offered a data file as an appendix to a volume of their own journal-like regular communication “Epidemiologisches Bulletin” [13], in which mRNA-I rates between CW52 in 2020 and CW52 in 2021 were available for the age cohorts of ‘0-17’, ‘18-29’, ‘30-39’, ‘40-49’, ‘50-59’, ‘60-69’, ‘70-79’, and ‘80+’ year old. However, these data only covered first and second doses. Currently, the RKI offers a github repository [14], at which various data sets around the mRNA-I process are made available. We downloaded all files concerning the weekly “Impfquote” (cumulative mRNA-I rates) for whole Germany and extracted relevant cumulative mRNA-I rates between CW37 in 2019 and CW46 in 2023. Thereby, we took into account changes in age cohort resolution as well as changes in mRNA-I status declaration.

For example, in September 2021 these were
Impfungen_gesamt, *Impfungen_gesamt_min1*, *Impfungen_gesamt_voll*, *Impfungen_gesamt_boost*, *Impfquote_gesamt_min1*, *Impfquote_12bis17_min1*, *Impfquote_18plus_min1*, *Impfquote_18bis59_min1*, *Impfquote_60plus_min1*, *Impfquote_gesamt_voll*, *Impfquote_12bis17_voll*, *Impfquote_18plus_voll*, *Impfquote_18bis59_voll*, and *_60plus_voll* ,

while in September 2023 these were

Impfungen_gesamt, *Impfungen_gesamt_min1*, *Impfungen_gesamt_00bis04_min1*,
Impfungen_gesamt_gi, *Impfungen_gesamt_00bis04_gi*, *Impfungen_gesamt_boost1*,
Impfungen_gesamt_boost2, *Impfungen_gesamt_boost3*, *Impfungen_gesamt_boost4*,
Impfquote_gesamt_min1, *Impfquote_05bis17_min1*, *Impfquote_05bis11_min1*,
Impfquote_12bis17_min1, *Impfquote_18plus_min1*, *Impfquote_18bis59_min1*,
Impfquote_60plus_min1, *Impfquote_gesamt_gi*, *Impfquote_05bis17_gi*,
Impfquote_05bis11_gi, *Impfquote_12bis17_gi*, *Impfquote_18plus_gi*, *Impfquote_18bis59_gi*,
Impfquote_60plus_gi, *Impfquote_gesamt_boost1*, *Impfquote_12bis17_boost1*,
Impfquote_18plus_boost1, *Impfquote_18bis59_boost1*, *Impfquote_60plus_boost1*,
Impfquote_gesamt_boost2, *Impfquote_12bis17_boost2*, *Impfquote_18plus_boost2*,
Impfquote_18bis59_boost2, and *Impfquote_60plus_boost2* .

Eventually, we discriminated between the age cohorts ‘0-17’ (juveniles), ‘18-59’ (adults), and ‘60+’ years of age (seniors). In order to register the three age cohorts to the finer resolution of AMR data, we proceeded as follows: For dose one and two, the mRNA-I rates of cohorts ‘0-17’ and ‘18-29’ were summarised to yield the cohort ‘0-29’, thereby being weighted by their demographic cardinality. The remaining age cohorts were kept as presented by the RKI. For dose three and four, the age cohorts ‘60-69’, ‘70-79’, and ‘80+’ were all assigned the mRNA-I rates of the ‘seniors’ group. The age cohorts ‘30-39’, ‘40-49’, and ‘50-59’ were all assigned the mRNA-I rates of the ‘adults’ group. The age cohort ‘0-29’ was again assigned a weighted value of the ‘juveniles’ and ‘adult’ group’s cumulative mRNA-I rates. For each of these, we listed (by differentiation) the weekly mRNA-I rates for doses one to four. Due to some apparent data updates in the RKI files, this difference might yield negative values, see for example CW39 in 2022 (Fig. 6). In the result section, we refer to ‘normalised incidence of mRNA-I’ meaning the age-specific weekly mRNA-I rate, normalised by cohort size.

2.3. Modelling of excess all-cause mortality counts (EAMC)

The methodology for estimating expected AM counts (expAMCs), and thereby excess AM counts (EAMCs), is based on our earlier work [4] and extended here with improved wealth of detail. As before, EAMC was computed for each age cohort as the difference between the observed all-cause mortality count (AMC) and its corresponding modelled expAMC. The all-cause mortality rate (AMR) was defined as the AMC over a given interval (typically a week, season, or year) divided by the size of the cohort, denoted N_{coh} .

To model expected mortality, we fitted an exponential decay function to the observed AMR data for each cohort over the period 2000-2019. As a novel feature, we conducted this fit not for yearly AMR data, but for each calendar week (CW) separately. Specifically, the expected normalised AMR (expNAMR), denoted $\tilde{r}_{AM,\text{coh}}^{\text{exp}}(t)$, was modelled as:

$$\tilde{r}_{AM,\text{coh}}^{\text{exp}}(t) = (1 - b_{\text{coh}}) \cdot \exp(-a_{\text{coh}} \cdot (t - t_0)) + b_{\text{coh}}, \quad (1)$$

where $t_0 = 2000$ is the reference year, and a_{coh} , b_{coh} are cohort-specific parameters determined via non-linear least squares fitting using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm (`fit` routine, MATLAB v2024b). As in our prior work, NAMR was normalised to the AMR value in the reference year, i.e. it holds $\tilde{r}_{AM,\text{coh}}^{\text{exp}}(2000) = 1$ allowing comparability across time and cohorts. In contrast to our earlier model however, the present version allows the asymptotic value b_{coh} to exceed 1, accommodating saturation in older cohorts *above* the level of the year 2000.

Once fitted, the expNAMR curves were multiplied by the cohort’s actual AMR in the year 2000 to obtain expAMR ($r_{AM,\text{coh}}^{\text{exp}}(t)$), and subsequently multiplied by $N_{\text{coh}}(t)$ to yield expAMC. Subtracting these from observed AMC values provides the EAMC for each cohort and time point. To estimate total expAMC and EAMC for the entire German population, cohort-level values were summed up. This approach further enables projection beyond 2019 by extrapolating the fitted expNAMR functions, using the forecast demographic data.

2.4. Confidence intervals and significances

For each cohort and each weekly expAMC estimates calculated above for the years 2000-2024, we determined 95% confidence intervals (CI), using the MatLab routine `predint`, which account for the fluctuations in the observed AMC data points over the time period of fitting. CI radii for the whole population were obtained by taking the square-root of the sum of the squared weighted-age-cohort-CI radii, according to the variance sum theorem. Observed AMC that exceeded the CI was termed ‘significant over-mortality’, while those that fell below the CI were termed ‘significant under-mortality (UM)’.

When comparing the relative frequency distributions (plotted in histograms) of values of normalised excess AMR (NEAMR), we used a Welch test to check for significant differences in mean values, as the prerequisites for a *t*-test (equal standard deviation of samples) was generally not met.

2.5. Cross-correlation analysis

To assess whether cohort-level AM patterns were temporally associated with PCR-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection or mRNA-I activity, we conducted a cross-correlation analysis between incidence data and NEAMRs. These analyses were performed separately for each age cohort and within two key time intervals of interest. The first interval (CW04 to CW42 of 2021) corresponds to the dominance of the ‘alpha’ variant and the early ‘delta’ phase in Germany – prior to the widespread administration of third (booster) mRNA-I doses. The second interval (CW30 of 2021 to CW03 of 2022) encompasses the main ‘delta’ wave

and the height of the booster campaign, while largely excluding the first and second mRNA-I doses.

For each cohort and time interval, we calculated Pearson correlation coefficients between a NEAMR time series and the following predictors: (i) weekly PCR-positive incidence, (ii) weekly mRNA-I incidence (doses 1-4), and (iii) the week-wise product of both incidence types as a proxy for joint exposure. These correlation coefficients were computed as a function of temporal lag (in weeks), with negative lags representing incidence events that occurred *before* observed changes in NEAMR. This reflects a causal hypothesis framework: that infection or injection events may precede and potentially influence AM trends, whereas reverse causation – NEAMR causing PCR or mRNA-I incidence – is implausible at the population level.

Interpretation of the cross-correlation follows standard convention: A correlation coefficient of 0 indicates no linear statistical association. Positive values indicate in-phase changes: increases in incidence tend to be followed by increases in NEAMR. Negative values indicate anti-phase changes: increases in incidence tend to be followed by decreases in NEAMR. For example, under the assumption of mRNA-I efficacy, one would expect that increased mRNA-I incidence should lead to a subsequent *decrease* in EM, reflected by negative correlation values at negative time lags (i.e. mRNA-I preceding reduction in NEAMR). Conversely, a positive correlation at negative lags could be expected between NEAMR and PCR-positive incidence, indicating that huge SARS-CoV-2 waves were followed by subsequent increases in AM.

By examining the lag-dependent correlation structure, we aim to identify whether any temporal relationships emerge between cohort-specific incidence metrics and subsequent EAM signals.

3. Results

This section presents the main findings of our age-resolved, weekly analysis of AM in Germany from 2000 through 2024. We begin by modelling expected AM trends for each age cohort using exponential functions fitted to pre-pandemic data. These models provide the baseline against which observed AM is compared, allowing the calculation of normalised EAM rates (NEAMR).

We then explore temporal patterns of NEAMR at high resolution, focusing on both individual weeks and aggregated seasons. The analysis captures historically consistent mortality features, but also highlights a series of atypical and persistent NEAMR signals beginning in late 2020 – particularly in specific age groups. These patterns are further examined in relation to SARS-CoV-2 PCR-positive incidence and mRNA-I uptake, using lagged cross-correlation analysis to identify potential temporal associations.

Taken together, the results provide a detailed temporal and demographic characterisation of EAM across the SARS-CoV-2 era, with particular attention to cohort-specific dynamics and structural shifts not visible at the population level alone. All analyses presented below for the total population are also available separately for males and females; corresponding figures and results can be found in Appendix A.

3.1. Weekly expNAMRs

Figure 1 shows the courses of model-estimated expected normalised all-cause mortality rates (expNAMRs) over 25 years for 5-year, sex-pooled age cohorts (index ‘ coh ’) in Germany. These expNAMRs were obtained by fitting the cohort-specific exponential function (Eq. 1) to the yearly observed NAMR values within each CW from 2000 to 2019, using least-squares estimation of the parameters a_{coh} and b_{coh} . The resulting fits were extrapolated beyond 2019.

Each 3D panel (labelled by age cohort) contains a family of 52 monochromatic lines, one for each CW, showing the expNAMR course over time (left to right) from the year 2000 (‘0’ on the ‘year’ axis) onwards. The lines are colour-coded from dark blue (CW01 or ‘1’ on the ‘week’ axis) to dark red (CW52 or ‘week 52’). For a given CW in a given year, multiplying the expNAMR value by (i) its reference value (the observed AMR in 2000) and (ii) the cohort size for that year yields the expected number of deaths in that week.

Most expNAMR trajectories exhibit a decreasing exponential trend from 2000 onwards; for cohort 50-54, the trend is nearly linear. Only in the eldest cohorts – 95+ and 90-94 (especially in late winter weeks) – do expNAMRs increase over time.

3.2. Weekly AMCs, expAMCs, and NEAMRs from 2000 through the ‘first Corona wave’ in early 2020

Figure 2 displays weekly AMCs (magenta) and expAMCs (black) for the same age cohorts as in Fig. 1 over 25 years. The expAMC for the total population (top panel, black line) shows a pronounced seasonal pattern, strongly sawtooth-shaped rather than sinusoidal. Its peak typically occurs shortly after New Year, near the end of fls_2 of the preceding year. Since around 2010, minor fluctuations have emerged, including a local minimum in mid-December and a local maximum near the end of June.

Figure 3 condenses the AMC and expAMC data into NEAMR, i.e. the (expAMC-)normalised difference between observed (AMC) and expected (expAMC) mortality. Red points indicate weeks of NEAMR exceeding the 95% CI (grey area); green points indicate weeks of NEAMR falling below it. A notable double peak in 2003 – February and July – is seen across nearly all age cohorts, especially those older than 54, with the 30-34 cohort as an exception, peaking only in July. Cohorts 70-74 and 80-84 experienced prolonged EAM in both 2002 and 2003.

Smaller but still significant EAM is detectable in cohorts 35-44, 45-49, and 50-54 in 2002. Singular EAM events occurred in summer 2001 among the 0-39 and 55-59 age groups, with another in early winter for the latter.

Subsequent EAM peaks occurred in winter seasons of 2008/09, 2012/13, 2014/15, 2016/17, and 2017/18, generally affecting those over 50. Minor summer peaks are also visible in 2006, 2010, 2015, and 2018. In contrast, the flu seasons 2018/19 and 2019/20 lacked the usual winter peak among those aged 55 and over.

Significant EAM at New Year 2020 was confined to the 35-39 age group (both sexes, see Figs. C.5, C.6). During the ‘first Corona wave’ (March 2020), significant EAM was observed in the 75-79 group, and for a brief period in 35-44 year old males. No significant EAM was recorded in other cohorts or in the total population. The EAM seen in 75-79 year old during this period appears due to the tail end of the seasonal pattern extending unusually wide into early 2020, with the magnitude of observed AMC only marginally above expAMC.

3.3. Patterns of NEAMR from mid 2020 through 2024

Following the significant EM peak in late December 2020, the German population experienced several waves of atypical (Fig. 3, top panel) and persistent Fig. 4 EAM through to the end of 2024. These patterns were strongly age-dependent and varied in timing, duration, and magnitude across cohorts (Fig. 3).

The whole population’s NEAMR signal pattern (Fig. 3, top panel) reveals four distinct winter EAM peaks – each occurring in December of 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023 – followed by consistent under-mortality (UM) dips in January or February. The 2020 peak emerged sharply from a previously unremarkable year, reaching around 25% NEAMR. The 2021 peak began earlier, with NEAMR rising above the 95% CI already in October. In 2022, the winter peak was preceded by a steady rise from July, culminating in a NEAMR near 30% – the highest of the period. In 2023, the rise occurred again in November, peaking in December at about 14%. The 2024 signal remained within the CI after an early-year UM dip, suggesting a year of considerable UM.

Annual EAMCs corroborate this picture of being atypical and persistent (Fig. 4, middle panel, left). A slight UM of -7,359 occurred in 2020, followed by moderate EAMCs in 2021 (25,361), and a notably significant value in 2022 (60,991), on par with the significant 2003 peak (42,526), when SARS-CoV(-1) spread in winter 2002/03. These updated values, based on refined modelling with weekly resolution and sex-separated 5-year cohorts, exceed earlier estimates by 12,000-18,000 deaths [4] (orange symbols in Fig. 4, top ; main model revision: now 5-year age cohorts, and summing over 52 weeks). EAMCs in 2023 and 2024 then dropped to moderate EAM (12,377) and considerable UM (-32,124), respectively. In the following, the main features of the age cohorts’ NEAMR signal patterns (Fig. 3) are summarised, in order of age, from the eldest (bottom panel) to the youngest (second topmost panel).

The significant EAM peak of the whole population in late December 2020 (see again top of Fig. 3) was consistently reflected by the signals in all age cohorts, except for the youngest (0-34-year old) and all females younger than 60 years old (Fig. C.5); as a second deviation to the general synchronicity in the late December EAM peak, a slightly delayed peak (CW02 in 2021) could be observed in both females (Fig. C.5) and males (Fig. C.6) of age 50-54 years.

The significance of atypical, persistent EAM since the end of 2020 until the end of 2024 is eye-catching in both the older (above 60 years, 75-79 in particular) and the younger (35-49); it is less pronounced in the eldest (95+), those 50-59, and the youngest (0-34). In the following, we attempt some systematic characterisation, sorting, and differentiation of the time patterns of EM.

The NEAMR pattern of the whole population (top of Fig. 3) from 2020 through 2023 is stereotyped, namely, characterised by four distinctive, sawtooth increases in series, each one peaking towards the mid or end of December, with always a subsequent dip to likewise significant UM in January, partly into February. In 2020, the NEAMR starting level of the sawtooth is within the 95% CI until November (to recall, the ‘first Corona wave’ being totally insignificant), with an about 25% NEAMR peak in late December; in 2021, the 95% CI is exceeded already in October, and NEAMR rises to a peak of nearly the same magnitude as in December 2020; in 2022 then, there is a roughly linear NEAMR increase from the January 2022 dip, with NEAMR rising above 95% CI already in July, and reaching a sharp peak of about 30% NEAMR magnitude in mid December, which is higher than those of the winters 2020 and 2021; in 2023, after the third January dip to UM in the wake of an EAM peak, the NEAMR signal remains in the 95% CI only until again rising above the 95% CI at the beginning of November, rising to the fourth significant NEAMR December peak in a row, at about 14% NEAMR level. The subsequent and significant NEAMR dip in early 2024 extends into April, and the NEAMR remains in the 95% CI until the end of 2024, which explains a distinct but less than significant UM for whole 2024 (Fig. 4, top, middle).

We now turn towards the NEAMR signals of the age cohorts (panels below top one in Fig. 3), starting with the eldest (bottom panel in Fig. 3), and running through to the youngest.

In those 95 years and older, there has practically been persistent UM since 2014 until summer 2020. By the way, in the period right before, i.e. from late 2011 until the flu season in early 2013, the excessive 95+ EAM occurred in the generation born in world war one; for this generation, corresponding significant EAM signals can be found in 2007/2008 in the 90-94 cohort, and in 2002/2003 (SARS-CoV-1) in the cohort 85-89. In December 2020, the population-wide significant EAM is fully reflected in those 95 and older. However, in contrast to all younger cohorts down to those at least 35 years old, there was no significant EAM in entire 2021, only very moderate EAM from October until mid December. After the typical (but slight in this period) EAM dip in early 2022, the NEAMR rose to first insignificant (i.e. moderate) EAM in summer 2021, and then two significant peaks, in October 2022, and again a higher one in late December 2022, only to fall to UM practically during whole 2023, and again in 2024 through its end.

The NEAMR signals of the two age cohorts 90-94 and 85-89 are very similar to each other, with their NEAMR patterns indeed strongly resembling that of the 95+ from late 2020 through 2022, but being more pronounced than for the eldest: Three significant EAM peaks into early January occurred during each Decembers 2020, 2021, and 2022, with average mortality or slight UM in 2023 like in the 95+, including a minor EAM peak in December 2023, and UM through 2024.

The age cohort 75-79 is the one most massively struck by EAM from 2020 through 2024, with significant EAM practically persisting from the ‘first Corona wave’ in March 2020 through end of 2024. Only, the distinctive NEAMR dips in the early year interrupted in 2021, 2022, and 2023 continuously significant NEAMR signals, with a more prolonged interruption in 2024 until summer, and the significant EAM pattern in late 2024 flu season being not peak-like, but due to almost constant EAM since late summer 2024.

The NEAMR patterns of the two cohorts 80-84 and 70-74 adjacent to 75-79 are again very similar to each other, and differ from the 90-94 and 85-89 in that they additionally show significant EAM in the winters 2023, and even shortly in late autumn 2024. In contrast to the 75-79, their late year EAM periods are not that excessively long, but lasted for about four weeks, plus a few weeks longer in the most extraordinary late 2022 EAM period, like also visible in the 90-94 and nearly in the 95+.

In the age cohort 65-69, the lengths of the five early winter periods of significant EAM are in-between those of the 75-79 and 70-74 or 80-84, respectively. Therefore, from late 2020 through 2024, this age cohort is the second most EM-struck in those older than 60 (the cohort 45-49 a little more, and the 35-39, 40-44 massively, see further below). The cohort 60-64 is slightly less struck, with their pattern resembling those of the 70-74 or 80-84, respectively, however, on the one hand, an EAM period missing at the end of 2024, but, on the other hand, showing prolonged EAM periods at the end of 2021, and a significant EAM period occurring in spring 2021, both latter phenomena shared by the 65-69 cohort (and 75-79).

The cohort 55-59 is the one least struck by EM. There is only one week of significant EAM in December 2020, four weeks in December, and three weeks in December 2022, the latter showing the highest magnitude, in accordance with this phenomenon being a consistent feature within the whole population, and all age cohorts alike. In the 55-59-year old, the early year dips in EAM even reach levels of significant UM, interestingly consistently from 2020 until 2024, and in 2024 significant UM being almost persistent until the end of the year.

The EAM pattern of the 55-59-year old resembles those of the older cohorts, with pretty clear and outstanding peaks in late years 2020, 2021, and 2022, and subsequent dips in early years. In principle, this is also the pattern in the cohort 45-49. However, in that cohort, first of all, the magnitude of the late 2020 EAM peak is much lower than those in 2021 and 2022 (and consists of only two weeks of significant EM), and those of the cohorts older than 60 years; second, and what is more in the 45-49 cohort, an EAM peak amplitude most massive of all cohorts occurs in December 2023. Then, after the subsequent dip in January and February, the NEAMR signal rises roughly linearly until the end of 2024 into significant EAM from autumn on. Overall, there is no EAM during the years 2020-2024.

In the cohorts 50-54, and the younger to youngest, 40-44-, 35-39-, 30-34-, and 0-29-year old, the patterns of the NEAMR signals are different from those 60 and older (and the 45-49-year old), in that higher frequency fluctuations become more dominant than the distinctive yearly sawtooth-dip patterns of the older.

In the 50-54, there are three lower yet significant NEAMR amplitudes in 2021, in January, in April and in December, further three such peaks in summer 2022, early autumn, and around New Year into 2023, and one in January 2024. The overall EAM is low during the years 2020-2024.

Also, the overall EAM is low to vanishing in the cohort 30-34, There are only two significant EAM peaks: one in summer 2022, and one at the end of December. The character of the EAM pattern has apparently not changed in 2020-2024 as compared with the twenty years before, since 2000.

In the youngest cohort 0-29, the NEAMR pattern from 2000 on (second topmost panel of Fig. 3) has evidently changed since autumn 2020. First, there was an atypical, pronounced dip into significant UM from mid December through February 2021, followed by a rise to significant EAM in May. A second atypical NEAMR dip to a longer UM period, including several weeks of significant values, from December 2021 through February 2022 followed, only to let NEAMR rise to persistent EAM from May through the end of 2022, with a final peak of significant EAM in whole December. During entire 2023 then, NEAMR remained within the 95% CI, with not even any tendency to net EAM or UM. However, towards the end of 2023, NEAMR rose into EM, persistent for about one year until autumn 2024, topped by an atypically long period of about six weeks of significant EAM in late spring, early summer of 2024. Altogether, there seems to have been overall EAM in both 2022 and 2024, at least for months-long periods, which is analysed more precisely in the subsequent Sec. 3.4.

Besides the age cohort 75-79, the cohorts 40-44 and 35-39 are those most massively struck

by EM, clearly less during the year 2020, but certainly from April 2021 on through 2024, with only a short period of ‘back to normal’ in summer 2023. At the turn of 2019 into 2020, as already mentioned in Sec. 3.2, there was a salient significant EAM peak in the 35-39-year old. Furthermore, there was a significant EAM peak in both cohorts 40-44, 35-39 in mid of March 2020, a week later than significance level was exceeded in the 75-79, and low yet significant EAM in late December. In these two age cohorts, the clearly increased oscillatory NEAMR amplitudes particularly in 2021 and 2024, as compared with the decades before 2019, strike the eye; likewise does so the persistence of EAM since 2021 through 2024 in these cohorts. Next, we investigate such persistent periods of EAM by averaging the NEAMR signal of each age cohort over three seasons a year, i.e. each about seventeen weeks long.

3.4. Seasonal NEAMRs

Figure 5 presents a contracted, seasonally averaged version of the NEAMR data from Fig. 3, providing a broad overview of mortality trends across age cohorts over 25 years. Where helpful, we refer to negative NEAMR values (UM) as ‘UM’, and positive values as simply ‘EAM’.

Prior to 2020, only one season showed significant EAM in the whole population (top of Fig. 5): summer 2003 (sus_{03}). Between then and 2019, five seasons displayed significant UM. Notably, the flu season $\text{fls}_{1,20}$ – which included the ‘first Corona wave’ – also exhibited significant UM; all $\text{fls}_{1,\text{year}}$ from 2020 through 2024 showed slight to significant UM, whereas there were three consecutive $\text{fls}_{2,\text{year}}$ seasons (2020-2022) with significant EM, followed by moderate EAM in $\text{fls}_{2,23}$, and minimal EAM in $\text{fls}_{2,24}$.

The histogram for the whole population (bottom panel of Fig. 5, top-left sub-panel) highlights two main observations: (i) average EAM in 2020-2024 is not significantly higher than in 2000-2019; and (ii) two seasonal peaks (both fls_2) in 2020-2024 exceeded any EAM in the prior 20 years, while two other seasons (both fls_1) showed more extreme UM than any earlier season. These extremes effectively balance each other out, rendering the overall difference between the two periods statistically insignificant.

However, closer inspection of the seasonal NEAMRs for individual age cohorts (top panel) and their corresponding frequency distributions (bottom panel) reveals some details otherwise hidden behind the lumped, whole-population statistics. For example, the major EAM peak in summer 2003 originated primarily in older cohorts (particularly 70-74 and 85-89). In contrast, distinct EAM during 2020-2024 occurred in multiple cohorts across a wide age range.

The 5-year cohort resolution reveals that the winter EAM peaks (fls_2) of 2020-2024 involved nearly all age cohorts, especially from 2021 onward. Exceptions include the youngest groups (0-29 and 30-34), the consistently robust 55-59 cohort, and somewhat unexpectedly, the 85-89 and 95+ cohorts. While the oldest cohorts did contribute to population-level EAM in $\text{fls}_{2,21}$ and $\text{fls}_{2,22}$, their own seasonal NEAMR distributions (histograms) show no significant difference between 2000-2019 and 2020-2024. That is, although their EAM may have been notably high in specific seasons, their average mortality did not increase significantly.

In sharp contrast, the 40-49 age group – broadly corresponding to the ‘school-child parent’ demographic – exhibited unprecedented EAM since December 2020. Both their seasonal NEAMR values (top panel) and their distributional shifts (bottom panel) confirm this. The differences between the two historical periods are highly significant ($p < 0.001$) in the 35-44 age group, strongly significant ($p < 0.01$) in 45-49, and weakly significant ($p < 0.05$) in 50-54.

While the whole population’s EAM in three consecutive fls_2 seasons (2020-2022) is visually prominent, it does not translate into a statistically significant shift in the NEAMR

distribution over time. The same holds for the youngest cohort: although they exhibited extremes of both UM and EAM in 2020-2024, all values remain within the historical range observed in 2000-2019. Similarly, while the 60-64 and 70-74 cohorts contributed to significant seasonal EAM in $fls_{2,21}$ and $fls_{2,22}$, their distributions also do not show significant shifts. In contrast, average NEAMR in 2020-2024 was strongly significantly higher in those 65-69 ($p < 0.01$) and 75-79 ($p < 0.001$) year olds, and the 75-79 cohort in particular was the dispositive contributor to the whole population’s seasonal NEAMR pattern (top panel of Fig. 5).

Interestingly, the 30-34 and 55-59 cohorts are the only ones to exhibit weakly statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) UM in 2020-2024 compared with 2000-2019.

3.5. Weekly courses of NEAMR, PCR-positive tests, and mRNA-I in 2020-2023

Figure 6 provides an overview of weekly NEAMR signals from 2020 to 2024 (reproduced with a coarser age resolution suited for matching incidence data; see Sec. 2.2.5), overlaid with rates (i.e. normalised incidences) of SARS-CoV-2 PCR-positive tests and mRNA-I. Having already described the NEAMR patterns in detail, we focus here on the broad temporal features of infection and mRNA-I rates.

PCR-positive incidence captures the rise of early SARS-CoV-2 variants (grouped as ‘other variants’), including the ‘first Corona wave’ (peaking in March 2020) and the ‘second wave’ (peaking in CW52, 2020). The ‘third wave’ (‘alpha’ variant) peaked around CW16 (mid-April 2021), with incidence rates similar to the second wave among cohorts aged up to 59, but increasingly lower in older cohorts.

The first two mRNA-I doses were largely administered by CW30 (late July 2021). Already during the mRNA-I campaign ceasing, in June 2021, the ‘delta’ variant emerged, with its first peak (‘fourth wave’) in CW35 (early September), and a second peak (‘fifth wave’) in CW47-48 (late November to early December). The booster campaign (third doses) began around CW40 (October 2021) for those over 60, and around CW45 (mid-November) for younger cohorts. Notably, the booster campaign was started in the younger cohorts almost concurrently with the ‘delta’ incidence peaking, and the ‘omicron’ variant emerged short before the booster campaign peaked on the whole population level in mid-December, CW50.

The taking over of the ‘omicron’ variant in mid-December 2021 coincided with extremely high PCR-positive rates throughout 2022 (temporarily reaching 60%) and into 2023, until test reporting ceased in CW41. At that point, PCR-positive incidences peaked again – reaching nearly 50% in the eldest, $\approx 20\%$ in the 30-39 cohort, and $\approx 10\%$ in the youngest. During the 18 months of monitored ‘omicron’ activity, four distinct ‘waves’ were observed in 2022, followed by two smaller ones in 2023.

3.6. Cross-correlations between NEAMR and SARS-CoV-2 incidence and mRNA-I data

Figures 7 and 8 summarise the results of our cross-correlation analysis between weekly NEAMR signals and age-cohort-resolved time series of PCR-positive SARS-CoV-2 test incidences, mRNA-I rates, and their products. We focus exclusively on negative time lags, which reflect the potential causal influence of these factors on subsequent mortality (see Sec. 2.5 for rationale).

During the first time interval (CW04 to CW42 of 2021; Fig. 7) – covering the period of dominance of the ‘alpha’ variant and the early ‘delta’ period (i.e. $fls_{1,21}$ and sus_{21}) – a negative correlation between the incidence of first-dose mRNA-I (mRNA-I1) and NEAMR was found only in the eldest cohort (80+). In this group, the correlation peaked at a lag of -1 week, with a very high absolute value of the coefficient (-0.93). Thus, the initiation of mRNA-I in this group coincided with or slightly preceded subsequent reductions in EM.

In contrast, no meaningful correlation between NEAMR and mRNA-I was observed in other cohorts during this period, with correlation coefficients either close to zero or weakly positive. An exception was the 30-39 year old cohort, in which a relatively strong positive correlation between the product of incidences of the second-dose mRNA-I (mRNA-I2) and the PCR-positive tests (PCR+ for ‘alpha’ variant: PCR+(alpha)), i.e. mRNA-I2×PCR+(alpha), and NEAMR was found at a lag of -18 weeks, with a peak coefficient of 0.86. The correlation between mRNA-I1×PCR+(alpha) and NEAMR, was similarly strong (0.84) at a lag of -20 weeks, which could be expected given the temporal proximity of mRNA-I2 to mRNA-I1. Interestingly, the corresponding NEAMR correlations with the mRNA-I2 (0.74, lag -13 weeks) and mRNA-I1 (0.75, lag -17 weeks) time series themselves were lower. Also interestingly, a moderately strong correlation was found between NEAMR and the PCR-positive incidence of the ‘delta’ variant, PCR+(delta), peaking at a lag of -1 week (value: 0.77), and PCR+(alpha), peaking at a lag of -21 weeks (value: 0.81). All this supports a close temporal association in the 30-39 year olds between observed EM, the initial mRNA-I campaign and transition to the ‘delta’ variant during summer 2021.

During the second interval examined (CW30 of 2021 to CW03 of 2022; Fig. 8) – covering the period of dominance of the ‘delta’ variant, including the peak of the booster campaign (i.e. second half of sus_{21} and $\text{fls}_{2,21}$) – correlation patterns became more stereotyped across age cohorts, less complex, and exhibiting one particularly dominant maximum. Across all cohorts aged 40 and above, NEAMR showed very strong positive correlations (0.93-0.99) with PCR-positive incidence of the ‘delta’ variant, with peak values occurring at or near zero lag. In the 30-39 year old, the peak correlation was more moderate (0.82, lag -2 weeks), and still strong in the eldest (approximately 0.88 at lag 0). The youngest cohorts again showed no substantial correlation with ‘delta’ incidence.

The booster (third-dose) campaign began in autumn 2021, during the height of ‘delta’ transmission. Accordingly, NEAMR showed similar correlation strengths with incidence of the third-dose mRNA-I (mRNA-I3) itself and with the joint variable mRNA-I3×PCR+(delta), both peaking close to the same lag (0 ± 1 weeks) as the direct correlation with PCR+(delta). This suggests a substantial overlap in timing between mortality changes and the simultaneous incidences of infection rates and mRNA-I3.

Positive correlations between NEAMR and both mRNA-I1 and mRNA-I2 were also observed in all cohorts during this ‘delta’ period, though generally weaker than those seen with PCR+ or mRNA-I3. Correlation coefficients with mRNA-I2 typically remained below 0.73, with the notable exception of the 30-39 year old, where a peak value of 0.84 was recorded at a lag of -6 weeks. Coefficients with mRNA-I1 were stronger, the highest value being 0.9 in the 30-39 year old (even higher than with mRNA-I3), and below 0.82 for all other age cohorts.

Taken together, these cross-correlation patterns suggest that mortality signals in all age cohorts older than 30 years were closely temporally aligned with both infection waves and mRNA-I campaigns during the mid- to late-2021 period.

Figure 1: German expected normalised AMRs (expNAMRs) of the lumped cohort of the youngest (ages 0-29 years), the thirteen older 5-year age cohorts, and the lumped cohort of the eldest (ages 95+); plotted are the curves fitted to the observed values of one specific CW in each year, with the observations themselves not shown for clarity of the figure; all observed (year-specific) AMR values were normalised to the CW's value in 2000; for each CW, an exponential two-parameter function (Eq. (1)) was fitted through the respective (twenty) observed normalised AMR (NAMR) data points from 2000 through 2019, as depicted by a line with a CW-specific colour ranging from blue (CW01) through violet (CW52, or CW53 in a leap year, respectively); for calculating prognoses (expAMR, expAMC, EAMR, NEAMR), each CW's fitted expNAMR function was extrapolated beyond 2019. Distinguishing females and males, the same is plotted in Fig. A.1 and Fig. A.2, respectively.

Figure 2: For the fifteen age cohorts resolving the complete age range, German ($N_{pop} \approx 83.6$ million in 2024 [15]) weekly observed (magenta lines) all-cause mortality counts (AMCs) and expected (model-estimated), corresponding values (expAMCs; black lines) from 2000 through 2024; an expAMC is the product of its correspondingly fitted expAMR value and the year-specifically observed number of cohort members (demographics; see e.g. [4, fig. 3]). Distinguishing females and males, the same is plotted in Fig. B.3 and Fig. B.4, respectively.

Figure 3: German weekly normalised excess AMRs (NEAMRs; black lines) from 2000 through 2024, for the same fifteen age cohorts as in Fig. 2; normalisation: weekly excess all-cause mortality count (EAMC: difference between its AMC and corresponding *expected* AMC (expAMC); both: see Fig. 2) divided by its expAMC; NEAMR values exceeding (red) or dropping below (green) the 95% CI indicated by a spot. Distinguishing females and males, the same is plotted in Fig. C.5 and Fig. C.6, respectively.

year	expAMC	EAMC	season	expAMC	EAMC
2000	838,448	-4,582	00/01	544,316	-8,864
2001	824,309	1,576	01/02	536,958	5,589
2002	815,786	23,139	02/03	532,318	33,253(**)
2003	809,753	42,526(**)	03/04	534,113	-2,574
2004	817,527	-4,384	04/05	538,075	7,909
2005	821,966	5,905	05/06	542,180	-9,188
2006	828,790	-9,128	06/07	546,094	-15,519
2007	833,498	-8,795	07/08	548,374	5,485
2008	835,511	4,216	08/09	553,866	15,208
2009	846,612	4,569	09/10	563,659	-13,571
2010	862,466	-5,891	10/11	567,296	-11,053
2011	860,407	-10,742	11/12	571,347	-2,577
2012	870,498	-5,808	12/13	576,878	22,890(**)
2013	876,724	14,808	13/14	586,351	-31,923(**)
2014	894,726	-29,267	14/15	598,299	18,289
2015	911,469	12,341	15/16	610,878	-28,210(**)
2016	930,430	-23,835	16/17	619,263	7,258
2017	938,046	-9,374	17/18	625,860	8,942
2018	948,239	4,055	18/19	635,716	-29,497(**)
2019	964,734	-27,950	19/20	647,699	-28,562
2020	982,632	-7,359	20/21	656,826	13,303
2021	992,943	25,361	21/22	663,690	21,985
2022	1,002,349	60,991(**)	22/23	671,067	40,709(**)
2023	1,013,493	12,377	23/24	683,167	-12,236
2024	1,034,630	-32,124	24/25	693,285	-38,746

season	fls _{1,20}	sus ₂₀	fls _{2,20}	fls _{1,21}	sus ₂₁	fls _{2,21}	fls _{1,22}	sus ₂₂	fls _{2,22}	fls _{1,23}	sus ₂₃	fls _{2,23}	fls _{1,24}	sus ₂₄	fls _{2,24}
whole pop.	-6.3	-1.7	11.5	-6.2	0.6	11	-3.3	7.8	17.7	-3.9	-1.2	7.6	-9.8	-1.5	3.2
0-29	-6.3	-2.8	-9.5	-10.8	3.9	1.2	-7	6.4	7.1	-0.3	-0.9	3	1.1	5	-1.1
30-34	-9.3	-6.5	-7.6	-6.3	-2.6	-0.6	-2.7	3.8	3.5	-5.3	-3.7	-1.3	-5.4	-7.4	-6.5
35-39	7.3	3.9	8.5	8.8	10.9	12.7	11.6	17	10.7	11	10.8	9	13.4	6.8	5.3
40-44	0.1	2.3	5.9	3.9	3.9	18.5	5.2	12.5	15.9	8.4	7.8	14.8	3.2	7.3	12.9
45-49	0.1	3.5	6.3	4.5	10.6	17.8	-1	4.4	16.8	-0.5	3.5	17.9	-3.7	4.8	14.8
50-54	-2.8	-2.5	1	4.3	2.4	11.4	1.1	7.1	12.3	4.2	2.5	8.2	4.6	0.1	1.5
55-59	-8.2	-3.4	0.6	-5	0.3	5.7	-8.3	-0.7	4.4	-8.6	-5.8	-2.6	-10.2	-8.4	-7.6
60-64	-3.2	-0.9	4.7	-0.5	2.7	11.6	-2	5	9.2	-1.6	-2.2	3.7	-6	-3.1	-3.4
65-69	-0.9	0.7	6.8	2.7	3.9	12.6	0.6	8	15	1.3	1.8	6	-3.9	-0.4	2.8
70-74	-8.9	-4.7	8.7	-2.5	3.1	13.7	-1.7	8.6	18.7	0.4	3.8	11.4	-3.1	3.1	7
75-79	8.9	10.8	21.6	10.9	13.3	20.4	5.4	19.1	26.9	6	11.6	18.6	-1.8	9.3	13.7
80-84	-10.7	-6.3	11.6	-9.6	-3.5	11.6	-3.4	7.6	21.5	-1.7	0.4	14	-4.9	3.3	8.4
85-89	-9.8	-4.4	11.5	-13.4	-5.7	5.8	-10.2	1.7	12.1	-11.7	-8.9	1.5	-16.5	-7.2	-1
90-94	-7	0.4	18.4	-9.6	2.2	12.9	-0.9	12.7	25	-3.8	-0.3	8.7	-16.3	-3.8	3.7
95+	-13.1	-4.1	7.8	-16.5	-2.4	4.7	-5.6	6.8	15.8	-12	-8.7	-1.5	-20.1	-8.8	-4

Figure 4: **top:** Yearly AMCs (i.e. observed: black dots) and expAMCs (i.e. expected: green triangles enclosed by 95% CIs), respectively, for the years 2000-2024 in Germany for comparison, expAMCs estimated by our original model version [4] (yearly instead of weekly NAMR resolution, 10-year instead of 5-year age cohorts: orange squares enclosed by 90% CIs); model population in 2024: $N_{pop} = 83.6$ million [15]; **middle, left:** yearly values of expAMCs and EAMCs (UM if negative); **middle, right:** the same for just the ‘flu seasons’ ($fls_{2,year}$ & $fls_{1,year+1}$: CW40-subscw20); 95%-CI significance of EAMC indicated by (**); **bottom:** seasonal percentage NEAMR values of the 5-year-resolved age cohorts since 2020 through 2024.

Figure 5: German seasonal NEAMRs from 2000 through 2024, for the same fifteen age cohorts as in Figs. 2,3; NEAMR values given in % as in Figs. 3,6, however, time-resolved more coarsely for just three seasons constituting a full year (**top**): a tile is plotted for each of the three seasons of any year ('flu season 1', fls1: CW04-CW20; 'summer season', sus: CW21-CW39; 'flu season 2', fls2: CW40-subscW03), which codes by colour the percentage NEAMR values averaged in time over the respective season (reddish: over-mortality, i.e. positive NEAMR; greenish: UM, i.e. negative NEAMR), now indicating significance by either an asterisk (NEAMR exceeding 95% CI) or a circle (NEAMR dropping below 95% CI); **bottom**: two distributions of the relative frequencies (histograms) of NEAMR values are plotted in one sub-panel, of which each reflects the data of one age cohort: one distribution for the years 2000-2019 (grey), and one for 2020-2024 (magenta); their arithmetic mean values are symbolised by solid vertical lines; the significance of the difference in mean values is indicated by star symbols: $p < 0.05$ (one), $p < 0.01$ (two), $p < 0.001$ (three); distinguishing females and males, the same is plotted in Fig. D.7 and Fig. D.8, respectively.

Figure 7: In Germany, during the time interval CW04-CW42,2021, and for seven age cohorts, the (Pearson) coefficients of cross-correlating their respective weekly NEAMR time course with several (time-lagged) normalised incidence signals (regarding normalisation, see caption of Fig. 6) are plotted: with the *normalised weekly numbers of positive PCR tests* PCR+(V) of two SARS-CoV-2 variants V=alpha,delta, and with the *normalised weekly number of mRNA-I* of the first (mRNA-I1), and second (mRNA-I2) mRNA-I, as well as with two products by week of incidences; maximum and minimum coefficient values to the right of a sub-panel; distinguishing females and males, the same is plotted in Fig. F.11 and Fig. F.12, respectively.

Figure 8: In Germany, during the time interval CW30,2021-CW03,2022, and for seven age cohorts, the (Pearson) coefficients of cross-correlating their respective weekly NEAMR time course with several (time-lagged) normalised incidence signals (regarding normalisation, see caption of Fig. 6) are plotted: with the *normalised weekly numbers of positive PCR tests* PCR+(V) of the SARS-CoV-2 variant V=delta, and with the *normalised weekly number of mRNA-I* of the first (mRNA-I1), second (mRNA-I2), and third (mRNA-I3) mRNA-I, as well as with one product by week of incidences; maximum and minimum coefficient values to the right of a sub-panel; distinguishing females and males, the same is plotted in Fig. G.13 and Fig. G.14, respectively.

4. Discussion

4.1. Prolonged population-wide PCR positivity and rising sick leave: an immunological hypothesis

The year 2022 marked an epidemiologically abnormal phase in the course of the SARS-CoV-2 era in Germany. With the rise of the ‘omicron’ variant, the normalised PCR-positive incidence (PCR+) rose to persistently high levels across all age cohorts (Fig. 6). Weekly PCR positivity ranged between approximately 0.4 (40%) in the youngest cohort and 0.2 (20%) in the eldest – levels that exceeded any previous peaks observed during the second wave (December 2020), the ‘alpha’ wave (spring 2021), or the ‘delta’ wave (autumn 2021). Remarkably, this unprecedented and enduring PCR positivity began precisely as the nationwide mRNA-I3 (‘booster’) campaign reached its peak in early December 2021.

We propose a hypothesis that connects this sustained PCR positivity to a broader population-level immune dysregulation. Specifically, we suggest that the cumulative effects of repeated mRNA-I – with approximately three doses administered to the majority of the adult population by the end of 2021 – may have temporarily impaired innate immune resilience, increasing susceptibility to both SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogens. This hypothesis is supported by a concurrent surge in non-CoViD-19 illness: Official figures from Destatis report a sharp rise in average annual sick days per employee from 11.2 in 2020 to 14.8 in 2022 and 15.1 in 2023, exceeding the previous historical maximum of 13.0 days in 1995 [16]. The AOK public health insurance consortium, covering nearly 30 million Germans, confirms this trend, reporting a surge in sick days from 19.7 in 2021 to 24.5 in 2022, and stably elevated values (23.9) in 2023 and 2024 [17, 18]. While numerous factors may have contributed to this rise, the coincidence of widespread mRNA-I, elevated sick leave, and persistent high PCR positivity suggests that immunological mechanisms merit closer examination.

Recent findings in molecular immunology provide plausible biological underpinnings for such an effect. Notably, studies have demonstrated that repeated exposure to SARS-CoV-2 spike protein (SP) – whether through infection or mRNA-I-induced expression – can epigenetically reprogram innate immune cells. Simonis et al. [19], for instance, showed that macrophages derived from mRNA-I-treated individuals exhibited persistent priming marked by histone H3K27 acetylation (H3K27ac) – an epigenetic marker of gene activation. Their study revealed a cumulative effect: three mRNA-I induced nearly nine times the number of acetylated promoter regions compared with one mRNA-I, with these changes persisting for at least six months. These modifications, associated with the activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome, predispose the immune system to heightened inflammatory responses upon subsequent stimulation.

This concept of trained immunity – while beneficial in some infectious contexts – may, under repeated or persistent antigen exposure, lead to dysregulation. Chronic activation of the NLRP3 inflammasome, e.g. by repeated SP presentation, has been linked to inappropriate cytokine release (e.g., IL-1 β [20]), increased systemic inflammation, and immune fatigue. Repeated presentation [20, fig. 4M] of the SARS-CoV-2 SP by *mRNA-I* in particular stimulates even prolonged and thus accumulative cytokine release, because any mRNA-I induces sustained SP production by body cells. Importantly, the same epigenetic signatures may reduce the effectiveness of the mucosal barrier by down-regulating protective antibodies such as IgA [21, 22], and can shift the balance toward inhibitory IgG4 antibodies that may impair long-term antiviral defence [23, 24].

Evidence from observational studies lends support to this interpretation. Some large-scale analyses suggest that individuals who received recent mRNA-I experienced an increased risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection compared with those mRNA-I-treated earlier [25, 26, 27]. While

confounding cannot be excluded, these findings are consistent with a temporary window of heightened vulnerability, potentially reflecting immune modulation rather than enhancement.

Lastly, the detection of SP or its fragments in circulation for extended periods – reportedly up to several months, and in some cases over a year [28] – raises additional concerns. Sustained expression of viral antigens within host tissues can be expected to act as a persistent, and thus fatiguing, immune stimulus, especially if SP production occurs in an uncontrolled or tissue- or organ-specific manner.

Taken together, the available epidemiological and molecular evidence suggests that the widespread deployment of mRNA-I had and continues to have unintended effects on immune homeostasis in a subset of the population. These effects could plausibly have contributed to prolonged PCR positivity during 2022 and beyond, and contribute to the observed sustained rise in general illness. Future studies should rigorously investigate these relationships using prospective, immunologically detailed cohort data.

4.2. Patterns of persistent EM and UM across generations

The emergence of persistent EAM patterns in specific age cohorts, both during and outside of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic period (in Germany, officially declared to end on April 7th, 2023)), raises important epidemiological and sociomedical questions. Most notably, we observed significant EAM from autumn 2021 onward in the age groups typically associated with parenthood of school-aged children, particularly the 40-49 year old and, even more distinctly, the 35-39 year old. These patterns are not only temporally consistent, but also statistically robust across multiple flu seasons (fls₂ of 2021 through 2024), with NEAMR values persistently exceeding the 95% confidence interval (Fig. 5).

What makes these findings more striking is their historical uniqueness: prior to autumn 2021, these cohorts exhibited only moderate fluctuations in mortality and were never among those contributing significantly to population-wide EM. We interpret this sudden and prolonged mortality signal as multifactorial. On the one hand, as elaborated in Sec. 4.1, immunological stress induced by repeated mRNA-I – particularly when administered within a short interval during ongoing viral circulation – may have compromised the immune robustness of these adults. On the other hand, this cohort also faced extraordinary psychosocial burdens due to school closures, remote working, and familial stress during the pandemic period [29]. The resulting chronic stress may have acted as a co-factor, weakening physiological resilience and thereby contributing to elevated AM.

Moreover, the most significant and continuous EAM is not seen in the 40-44 cohort but rather in the adjacent 35-39 group (histogram in Fig. 5 in particular), which exhibits sustained EAM even during non-winter seasons, such as summer 2022 – an unusual period for elevated AM outside of heatwave events. While EAM among 40-49 year old appears more oscillatory and is partially concealed at the population level due to their relatively lower absolute AMCs, the persistence and magnitude of NEAMR signals in both groups render this a demographically and epidemiologically exceptional phenomenon.

This current mortality anomaly invites comparison with earlier patterns in elderly cohorts. For instance, strong EAM signals were observed in 2003 among the 85-89 and 70-74 age groups. Subtracting their average age from the year, i.e. $2003 - 87 \approx 1916$ and $2003 - 73 \approx 1930$, points to cohorts born during World War I and those who were both born at the beginning of the Great Depression plus had to spend their childhood during World War II, respectively. These are generations likely shaped by early-life stressors, malnutrition, or trauma – factors known to influence long-term health trajectories [30, 31, 32, 33]. Five years later, in 2008, the same individuals had shifted into the 90-94 and 75-79 year old

cohorts, respectively, where again elevated AM was observed (albeit slightly below statistical significance), and again in 2012-2013, when this same war-affected generation reached 95+ years of age, EAM was prominent and, in parts, statistically significant. These longitudinal cohort traces suggest that early-life adversity may leave a lasting biological imprint that manifests as increased vulnerability in later life. While speculative, such a pattern aligns with existing theories of developmental origins of health and disease (DOHaD), which posit that prenatal and early childhood environments have long-term impacts on immunity, metabolic health, and life expectancy [32, 33].

During the SARS-CoV-2 era, another cohort – the 75-79 year old – showed remarkable and persistent EAM throughout 2020-2024, with almost no return to UM in any of the five flu seasons. This cohort was born in 1941-1949, i.e. during World War II and directly after, and would have partly lived their early child and formative years in post-war Europe, a time of reconstruction, nutritional scarcity, and psychological upheaval. The persistence and magnitude of their EAM signals suggest that they, too, represent a demographically vulnerable population, either due to physiological ageing, life-course exposures, or possible interactions with pandemic-era interventions, including mRNA-I.

In contrast, two age groups stood out for their consistent UM: the 30-34 year old and the 55-59 year old. These cohorts exhibited statistically significant negative NEAMR values across several seasons. Being born between 1986-1994 and 1961-1969, respectively, we cannot think of any concrete environmental causes for the consistent UM. One might speculate that either demographic resilience, lower exposure to iatrogenic or infectious risks, or differential mRNA-I timing or uptake played a role. Alternatively, selection bias in survival (e.g., the healthiest individuals being over-represented in these cohorts due to prior low mortality) could also contribute.

Taken together, the NEAMR patterns observed over nearly a quarter century suggest that EAM and UM are not randomly distributed across age groups and time, but may instead reflect a complex interplay of cohort-specific vulnerabilities, pandemic policy exposures, and biological stressors. While this analysis cannot establish causality, it does call for further investigation into the long-term health trajectories of historically distinct birth cohorts – especially in light of the post-2021 mortality anomalies among middle-aged adults and the previously war-affected elderly.

4.3. Cross-correlational evidence linking mortality to infection and injection timelines

To evaluate possible associations between EAM and epidemic markers, we analysed the correlation coefficients between NEAMR time courses and those of PCR-positive (PCR+) test rates, mRNA-I incidences, and their combinations. In accordance with our methodological framework (Sec. 2.5), we restrict our focus to negative time lags in the cross-correlation functions, which represent the temporal precedence of potential causative events (infections or injections) over mortality responses (Figs. 7, 8).

Two intuitive expectations guided this analysis: first, that PCR+ incidences should correlate *positively* with NEAMR, since they mark the spread of infection; and second, that mRNA-I incidences should correlate *negatively*, as mRNA-I were designed to reduce infection severity and mortality.

Surprisingly, in the time interval CW04-CW42 in 2021 (Fig. 7), the PCR+ incidence of the ‘alpha’ variant (PCR+(alpha)) correlated only moderately positively (coefficients maximally 0.68) with NEAMR during ‘alpha’ existence in the cohorts of the 40-49, 60-69, and 70-79 year old. In the youngest cohort (0-29), there was virtually no such correlation, while the 30-39 year old stood out with a notable positive coefficient of 0.81, peaking at a lag of -21 weeks. Evidently, PCR+(alpha) did not coincide with almost immediately subsequent

EM, but correlated with such about five months later. Moreover, in this cohort and during this time interval, the early presence of the ‘delta’ variant (its incidence: PCR+(delta)) showed a correlation with NEAMR nearly as high (0.77 at -1 week). More notably, the correlation between NEAMR and the products of PCR+(alpha) incidence and rates of mRNA-I1 or mRNA-I2, respectively, was even higher, namely, 0.84 and 0.86, respectively. All this strongly suggests a harmful synergistic effect: mRNA-I administered at the height of ‘alpha’ circulation may have temporarily impaired immune function in this cohort, particularly in males (Fig. F.12) more than females (Fig. F.11). Consequently, the subsequent ‘delta’ wave, which began circulating in June 2021, may have disproportionately affected individuals with recently altered or weakened immune responses.

This interpretation gains plausibility from several additional observations. First, the emergence of ‘delta’ was temporally aligned with the peak of mRNA-I1 and mRNA-I2 rates in the 0-29 cohort and mRNA-I2 rates in the 40-59 year old. Second, the first PCR+(delta) incidence peaks occurred earliest and strongest in the cohorts under 40 years old (Fig. 6). These temporal dynamics are compatible with the hypothesis that the ‘delta’ variant arose, at least in part, as a mutational response to high-volume SP exposure via mass mRNA-I campaigns during an active ‘alpha’ epidemic – a scenario contradicting classical epidemiological theory of appropriate inoculation strategies [34, 35, 36].

Further supporting this concern, exceptionally high NEAMR levels were observed during the second ‘delta’ wave in late 2021 (in the time interval from CW30 in 2021 to CW03 in 2022; Fig. 8), coinciding with comparably high PCR+(delta) incidence (Fig. 6) and strong to very strong positive correlations with NEAMR (coefficients 0.9-0.99, with lags 0-1 week) in all cohorts above age 40. The 30-39 year old again showed a weaker, though still considerable, correlation (0.82 at lag -5 weeks), while the youngest cohort (0-29) remained essentially uncorrelated.

An unexpected inverse correlation was noted in the eldest cohort (95+) during the ‘alpha’ period (Fig. 7, bottom panel): higher PCR+ rates were associated with lower NEAMR values. On closer inspection, this counterintuitive finding appears to be a statistical artefact. The peak in EAM among the eldest occurred during the ‘second wave’ in December 2020, followed by a characteristic (natural) dip to UM in early 2021 – a seasonal pattern well-documented for severe flu seasons. The period of sharply ceasing NEAMR coincided with the start of both ‘alpha’ circulation and the earliest stages of the mRNA-I campaign, which was prioritised for the elderly. Thus, this resulting (intuitively expectable) negative correlation with mRNA-I reflects a likely coincidental temporal overlap rather than a causal protective effect of mRNA-I.

In all other age cohorts, and across both time intervals studied, the correlations between NEAMR and mRNA-I rates were consistently positive – contrary to the expected protective effect. This pattern holds for both mRNA-I1 and mRNA-I2 during 2021, and for mRNA-I3 during the ‘booster’ campaign of late 2021 into 2022. Indeed, mRNA-I3 incidence was strongly positively correlated with NEAMR in all cohorts above age 50 (Fig. 8).

This alignment of mRNA-I campaigns with subsequent AM surges – most notably, the unprecedented December 2022 EAM peak (Fig. 4) – casts serious doubt on the population-level efficacy of the mRNA-I programme in reducing mortality. On the contrary, our findings support the concern that mass mRNA-I during active viral spread, particularly with novel, mRNA-based platforms and incomplete immunological understanding, may have produced unintended adverse outcomes, detectable in terms of significant EAM.

These observations are further corroborated by independent analyses. Kuhbandner and Reitzner [37, fig. 5] reported a positive correlation (up to $r = 0.85$) between regional mRNA-I coverage and changes in NEAMR across Germany’s 16 federal states. A similar association

was observed for stillbirth rates (up to $r = 0.72$) [37, fig. 6B]. While correlation does not imply causation, these robust, temporally and geographically consistent patterns warrant urgent further investigation.

5. Conclusion

Our presented methodology reveals clear and statistically significant patterns of excess and under-mortality across distinct age cohorts in Germany from 2000 through 2024. Notably, from autumn 2021 onward, adults aged 35-49 – representing the majority of school-aged children’s parents – have experienced persistent and recurrent excess all-cause mortality. This signal is historically unprecedented in that particular age group and concealed in whole-population aggregates due to relatively low absolute mortality.

These findings call for urgent and transparent scientific investigation. In light of the temporal proximity between these mortality anomalies and the nationwide rollout of SARS-CoV-2 mRNA injections – particularly during periods of ongoing viral transmission – possible immunological or iatrogenic contributions must be examined. The consistency, magnitude, and demographic specificity of the observed mortality patterns are not easily dismissed as statistical noise or incidental variation. Rather, they demand careful scrutiny from health authorities, epidemiologists, and policymakers. Future research should prioritise granular, cohort-resolved analyses over aggregate national statistics to detect and understand such associations and to reveal possible causation.

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Competing interests

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Authors’ contributions

Conceptualisation: MG and RR; draft: MG; calculations and figures: RR; writing, discussing, and revising: MG and RR.

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APPENDIX

A. For both sexes separately, the age cohorts' normalised AMRs (NAMRs)

Figure A.1: *Females*: German expected normalised AMRs (expNAMRs) with 5-year resolution of age cohorts; an expNAMR course is plotted over the years from 2000 through 2024 for a given CW (one line); see again the caption of Fig. (1) for details on normalisation, fitting, and extrapolation of these courses.

Figure A.2: *Males*: German expected normalised AMRs (expNAMRs) with 5-year resolution of age cohorts; an expNAMR course is plotted over the years from 2000 through 2024 for a given CW (one line); see again the caption of Fig. (1) for details on normalisation, fitting, and extrapolation of these courses.

B. For both sexes separately, the age cohorts' weekly observed AMCs, and the correspondingly expected (model-estimated) values (expAMCs), from 2000 through 2024

Figure B.3: *Females*: German weekly observed AMCs (magenta lines), and correspondingly expected values (expAMCs, black lines) from 2000 through 2024, for the same seven age cohorts as in Figs. 2,3,6.

Figure B.4: *Males*: German weekly observed AMCs (magenta lines), and correspondingly expected values (expAMCs, black lines) from 2000 through 2024, for the same seven age cohorts as in Figs. 2,3,6.

C. For both sexes separately, the age cohorts' weekly NEAMRs, from 2000 through 2024

Figure C.5: *Females*: German weekly NEAMRs (black lines) from 2000 through 2024, for the same seven age cohorts as in Figs. 2,3,6; values exceeding (red) or dropping below (green) the 95% CI indicated by a spot.

Figure C.6: *Males*: German weekly NEAMRs (black lines) from 2000 through 2024, for the same seven age cohorts as in Figs. 2,3,6; values exceeding (red) or dropping below (green) the 95% CI indicated by a spot.

D. For both sexes separately, the age cohorts' seasonal NEAMRs, from 2000 through 2024

Figure D.7: *Females*: German seasonal NEAMRs from 2000 through 2024, with 5-year resolution of age cohorts; NEAMR values calculated within three seasons constituting a year (**top**): 'flu season 1' (fls₁: CW04-CW20), 'summer season' (sus: CW21-CW39), and 'flu season 2' (fls₂: CW40-subscCW03); NEAMR values exceeding (reddish) or dropping below (greenish) the 95% CI (determined for each season) indicated by an asterisk or circle, respectively; **bottom**: the corresponding histograms for the time spans 2000-2019 (grey) and 2020-2024 (magenta), respectively, their arithmetic mean values symbolised by solid vertical lines; the significance of the difference in mean values is indicated by star symbols: $p < 0.05$ (one), $p < 0.01$ (two), $p < 0.001$ (three).

Figure D.8: *Males*: German seasonal NEAMRs from 2000 through 2024, with 5-year resolution of age cohorts; NEAMR values calculated within three seasons constituting a year (**top**): ‘flu season 1’ (fls₁: CW04-CW20), ‘summer season’ (sus: CW21-CW39), and ‘flu season 2’ (fls₂: CW40-subsCW03); NEAMR values exceeding (reddish) or dropping below (greenish) the 95% CI (determined for each season) indicated by an asterisk or circle, respectively; **bottom**: the corresponding histograms for the time spans 2000-2019 (grey) and 2020-2024 (magenta), respectively, their arithmetic mean values symbolised by solid vertical lines; the significance of the difference in mean values is indicated by star symbols: $p < 0.05$ (one), $p < 0.01$ (two), $p < 0.001$ (three).

E. For both sexes separately, the age cohorts' weekly NEAMRs, from 2020 through 2024, as well as incidences of (SARS-CoV-2-variant-specific) PCR+ and mRNA-I

Figure E.9: *Females*: German weekly NEAMRs (black lines) from 2020 through 2024, for the same seven age cohorts as in Figs. 2,3,6; see caption of Fig. 6 for detailed explanation of all symbols shown.

Figure E.10: *Males*: German weekly NEAMRs (black lines) from 2020 through 2024, for the same seven age cohorts as in Figs. 2,3,6; see caption of Fig. 6 for detailed explanation of all symbols shown.

F. For both sexes separately, cross-correlations during CW04-CW42,2021 of the age cohorts' NEAMR and some incidence signals

Figure F.11: In Germany, during the time interval CW04-CW42,2021, and for seven *female* age cohorts, the (Pearson) coefficients of cross-correlating their respective weekly NEAMR time course with several (time-lagged) normalised incidence signals (regarding normalisation, see caption of Fig. 6) are plotted: with the *normalised weekly numbers of positive PCR tests* PCR+(V) of two SARS-CoV-2 variants V=alpha,delta, and with the *normalised weekly number of mRNA-I* of the first (mRNA-I1), and second (mRNA-I2) mRNA-I, as well as with two products by week of incidences; maximum and minimum coefficient values to the right of a sub-panel; the same for both sexes together: see again Fig. 7.

Figure F.12: In Germany, during the time interval CW04-CW42,2021, and for seven *male* age cohorts, the (Pearson) coefficients of cross-correlating their respective weekly NEAMR time course with several (time-lagged) normalised incidence signals (regarding normalisation, see caption of Fig. 6) are plotted: with the *normalised weekly numbers of positive PCR tests* PCR+(V) of two SARS-CoV-2 variants V=alpha,delta, and with the *normalised weekly number of mRNA-I* of the first (mRNA-I1), and second (mRNA-I2) mRNA-I, as well as with two products by week of incidences; maximum and minimum coefficient values to the right of a sub-panel; the same for both sexes together: see again Fig. 7.

G. For both sexes separately, cross-correlations during CW30,2021-CW03,2022 of the age cohorts' NEAMR and some incidence signals

Figure G.13: In Germany, during the time interval CW30,2021-CW03,2022, and for seven female age cohorts, the (Pearson) coefficients of cross-correlating their respective weekly NEAMR time course with several (time-lagged) normalised incidence signals (regarding normalisation, see caption of Fig. 6) are plotted: with the *normalised weekly numbers of positive PCR tests* PCR+(V) of the SARS-CoV-2 variant V=delta, and with the *normalised weekly number of mRNA-I* of the first (mRNA-I1), second (mRNA-I2), and third (mRNA-I3) mRNA-I, as well as with one product by week of incidences; maximum and minimum coefficient values to the right of a sub-panel; the same for both sexes together: see again Fig. 8.

Figure G.14: In Germany, during the time interval CW30,2021-CW03,2022, and for seven *male* age cohorts, the (Pearson) coefficients of cross-correlating their respective weekly NEAMR time course with several (time-lagged) normalised incidence signals (regarding normalisation, see caption of Fig. 6) are plotted: with the *normalised weekly numbers of positive PCR tests* PCR+(V) of the SARS-CoV-2 variant V=delta, and with the *normalised weekly number of mRNA-I* of the first (mRNA-I1), second (mRNA-I2), and third (mRNA-I3) mRNA-I, as well as with one product by week of incidences; maximum and minimum coefficient values to the right of a sub-panel; the same for both sexes together: see again Fig. 8.